

DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING ACCORDING TO WORLD SCIENTISTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20830794>

Abstract. *This article explores the importance of critical thinking and highlights the significant contributions of educators in fostering and developing critical thinking skills among learners. Critical thinking is considered one of the most essential competencies in modern education, as it enables individuals to analyze information objectively, evaluate evidence, solve problems effectively, and make informed decisions. In an era characterized by rapid technological advancement and an abundance of information, the ability to think critically has become increasingly important for academic success and lifelong learning.*

Keywords: *reasoning, critical thinking, interest, scepticism, modesty.*

Critical thinking, reflective thinking, creative thinking, dialogic/dialectical thinking, decision-making, problem solving, and emotional intelligence are higher-order thinking skills that students need to develop. The fact that critical thinking can be developed through practice requires the implementation of thinking development exercises in the educational process¹.

Critical thinking is a skill that is receiving special attention from teachers these days. In particular, the possibility of developing critical thinking skills using artificial intelligence techniques has been examined². The effectiveness of the current education system can be enhanced by implementing artificial intelligence strategies to develop critical thinking skills in English literature lessons. Critical thinking refers to making logical and well-considered, well-founded judgments, and having an attitude that includes questions such as evidence and conclusions, rather than simply accepting all the evidence and conclusions that the student encounters. People who are good at critical thinking ask questions like, “How do you know this? Is this conclusion based on evidence or emotion?” and “Are there alternatives?” when presented with new information. Critical thinking can be broken down into three main skills:

Curiousness is the desire to learn more and seek out evidence, as well as being open to new ideas.

Skepticism involves asking healthy questions about new information and not blindly trusting the information presented.

Discernment is the ability to recognize that one’s beliefs and ideas are wrong when confronted with new, compelling evidence to the contrary.

The term “analytical thinking” refers to the increased focus on students’ understanding of algorithmic thinking, coding, and designing computational solutions to problems. This emphasizes children’s ability to engage with algorithms and programming, and helps develop skills such as logical reasoning, pattern recognition, abstract reasoning, and problem solving³.

¹ Bailin, S., Case, R., Coombs, J. R., & Daniels, L. B.. Common misconceptions of critical thinking. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 31(3), 1999. – P. 269–283. <https://doi.org/10.1080/002202799183124>

² Liu, W., & Wang, Y. The effects of using AI tools on critical thinking in English literature classes among EFL learners: An intervention study. *European Journal of Education*, 2024.

³ Angeli, C., & Giannakos, M. *Computational thinking education: Issues and challenges. Computers in Human Behavior*, 105, 106185. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.106185>

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Although analytical thinking is a term that originated in computer science from a technological perspective for automation, this type of thinking is also used today by those who want to learn, adopt, and predict life situations from other fields and groups⁴.

It is advisable to develop in students the ability to think based on laws, forms and methods, to give definitions, to work with concepts, to draw conclusions, to reveal contradictions, to systematize and classify existing knowledge.

It is clear from this that if we set ourselves the goal of training qualified personnel in the future, we should use exercises that develop logical thinking from the primary grades in teaching each subject.

Different methods and approaches are used in each lesson to help students analyze complex situations in order to develop logical thinking. In the process of developing reading, listening, and writing skills during exercises in English classes, students develop the ability to form basic mental operations (analysis, synthesis, classification, comparison, etc.), distinguish between reasonable and unreasonable judgments, and justify the stages of solving.

A.R. Smirnova identifies the trends of the development and interaction of psychological and logical thinking models and emphasizes that the formation of psychological and logical thinking models in children is a step-by-step and complex process, and their interaction is of decisive importance in the processes of education and upbringing. Emotional, creative, contextual thinking of a child, often based on personal experience, is called psychological thinking. According to A.R. Smirnova, logical thinking joins the child's psychologically reasonable conclusions, or logical thinking is strengthened by emotional thinking. A child's thinking develops both socially and independently using methods such as games, conversations, and question-and-answer⁵.

S.S. Shamsulloeva, having considered the development of logical thinking in the process of teaching biology, developed and tested the technique of logical thinking. This technique includes special methodological instructions, teaching materials, exercises, question-and-answer technologies⁶.

S.Yu. Kupchinaus in his dissertation developed didactic conditions for the development of constructive thinking in students studying algorithms and concepts, paying special attention to the project task. S.Yu. Kupchinaus emphasizes the importance of developing constructive thinking in students in understanding algorithms and concepts, and the need to create appropriate pedagogical conditions for the effective organization of this process. The process of analyzing and generating new ideas in order to solve real-life problems of students is called constructive thinking. Special attention is paid to project problems, as they help to consolidate students' theoretical understanding, as well as strengthen the ability to think algorithmically and create practical solutions. According to S.Yu. Kupchinaus, in order to develop constructive thinking based on algorithms, special didactic-based project activities should be included in the educational process⁷.

⁴ Padrón, N. P., Planchart, S. F., & Reina, M. F. *Approach to a definition of computational thinking. RIED. Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia*, 24(1), 55–76. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5944/ried.24.1.27419>

⁵ Смирнова А. П. Анализ моделей мышления: логический и психологический подход: Автореф. Дисс. ... канд. пед. Н. Санкт Петербург, 2005. – 19с.

⁶ Шамсуллоева С.С. Дидактические основы развития логического мышления в процессе обучения биологии (на материалах вузов Республики Таджикистан): Автореф. дисс. ... пед. н. 2014. – 26 с.

⁷ Купчинаус С. Ю. Дидактические условия развития конструктивно-логического мышления студентов - будущих педагогов-математиков: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. пед. н. Ижевск. 2006. – 20с.

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L.N. Fatkulloyeva proposed a variant of the optimal model of the process of forming a culture of logical thinking of future teachers. The culture of logical thinking of a person, in addition to being a set of mental processes, also reflects his methodological, ethical and cultural approach to thinking. Comparison, recognition of signs, differentiation of generality and specificity, grouping, guessing, drawing conclusions and supporting these conclusions are the elements that make up the culture of logical thinking. L.N. Fatkulloyeva concludes by emphasizing that the development of theoretical foundations and practical mechanisms of the educational process and the development of a culture of logical thinking in aspiring teachers should be its important and methodological component⁸.

According to the scientist, the uniqueness of a teacher's culture of logical thinking requires mastering logic based on formal and meaningful rules, being armed with a system of logical skills, knowledge of the logic of academic subjects and the logic of their presentation in lessons, teachers' willingness to develop students' logical thinking, and understanding the logic of the pedagogical process.

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⁸ Фаткуллова Л.Н. Формирование культуры логического мышления будущих учителей в условиях интегрального образовательного пространства: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. пед. н. Йошкар-ола, 2010. – 20с.

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